

CASTING PARTICULATE AND FIBROUS METAL-MATRIX COMPOSITES BY VACUUM INFILTRATION OF A LIQUID METAL UNDER AN INERT GAS PRESSURE

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ABSTRACT

Reported here is a new method of making metal-matrix composites. This method combines the essentials of three liquid-phase fabrication methods: (i) vacuum infiltration, (ii) infiltration under an inert gas pressure, and (iii) squeeze casting. In this method, the particulate or fibrous preform is placed in a chamber and the matrix alloy is placed above the preform. The matrix alloy is heated to the liquidus temperature together with the chamber and the preform under vacuum. Then an inert gas like argon is compressed on to the top surface of the matrix alloy melt, forcing the melt to infiltrate the preform. The pressure is 1,000 - 2,500 psi. Because the temperature of the melt is just at the liquidus, it is much lower than that in squeeze casting. Moreover, the pressure is an order of magnitude lower than that in squeeze casting. The low temperature lessens the interfacial reaction between the matrix and the filler, while the low pressure essentially eliminates preform compression. This method has been successfully used to fabricate aluminum-matrix composites reinforced by short ceramic fibers, continuous ceramic fibers, SiC particles, Al₂O₃ particles, graphite flakes and SiC whiskers.

INTRODUCTION

Metals with low densities, such as Al, Mg, Ti and their alloys, are usually chosen as the matrices of metal-matrix composites. A wide variety of ceramic, boron and carbon materials are used as reinforcements. Unfortunately, these liquid metals do not wet the surfaces of most commercial reinforcements [1-7].

In 1983, Toyota Motor Corporation announced its manufacture of composite pistons used in automotive diesel engines by squeeze casting [8]. In this method, a porous ceramic fiber preform was inserted into a die, and the aluminum alloy melt was poured into the preheated die located on the bed of a hydraulic press. The applied pressure made the molten aluminum alloy penetrate the fiber preform and bond the fibers. The composite aluminum pistons are far superior to unreinforced pistons [9-15].

The principle of the process described in this paper is similar to that of the squeeze casting, but, instead of a ram, an inert gas is used to press the liquid aluminum alloy into the preform. The melt temperature may be as low as the liquidus temperature for alloys with a temperature range between the liquidus and solidus, or near to the liquidus temperature for pure aluminum and the eutectic alloys. The rate at which the pressure is increased is quite low.

METHOD

The hot isostatic pressing (HIP) apparatus used in this work for preparing MMCs is schematically illustrated in Fig. 1. The chamber (steel)

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was evacuated using a mechanical vacuum pump. An inert gas (N₂ or Ar) bottle was connected to the chamber with tubes and a valve. If the pressure of the inert gas in the bottle was lower than 2,500 psi, a compressor must be used to increase the chamber pressure when needed. The chamber wall must be strong enough to sustain simultaneous high pressures and high temperatures, at least 2,500 psi at 665°C. The inner wall surface of the chamber was coated with a graphite paste for ease in demolding. Thermocouples 1 and 2 were in contact with the outer wall of the chamber, near to the aluminum alloy in the upper part and the preform at the bottom respectively. Before the high pressure gas was introduced into the chamber the temperature of the aluminum melt was allowed to drop to its liquidus temperature at a very low cooling rate. We can consider that the temperature in any part of the chamber was approximately the same. The heating element was made from graphite.

The process consists of seven steps, as illustrated in Fig. 2 and described below.

A₀-A₁: The aluminum ingot and the preform were put in the chamber, which was then sealed and evacuated to a pressure of 50 - 200 x 10⁻³ torr (9.7 - 38.7 x 10⁻⁴ psi).

A₁-A₂: The chamber and its charges were superheated at 50 - 100°C above the liquidus temperature of the alloy. In the mean time, evacuation continued.

A₂-A₃: The temperature was maintained for a period of time to ensure that the alloy melts completely and that the temperature of any part of the chamber was approximately equal.

A₃-A₄: The power input was gradually lowered until the temperature dropped to the liquidus or near to the liquidus temperature at the cooling rate of 0.5 - 3.0°C/min. Evacuation continued at the same time.

A₄-A₅: While the temperature was maintained, the evacuation was stopped. The valve connected to the inert gas bottle was opened. A pressure of 1,000 - 2,500 psi was applied to the surface of the melt to force the melt to penetrate the porous preform completely. A time of 30 seconds was needed to reach the pressure of 2,000 psi used in this work.

A₅-A₆: Once the predetermined pressure was reached, the heating element was turned off. In order to increase the cooling rate, a cooling water jacket outside the chamber was used. The pressure must be maintained during the solidification period and the cooling period afterward.

A₆-A₇: When the temperature was 30 - 50°C below the solidus, it was supposed that the composite had solidified completely. The outlet valve was then opened to release the inert gas. Premature release would result in shrinkages, cavities and cracks in the composite. The temperature continued to drop until it was below 300°C. The lid of the chamber was then opened. The composite material was then demolded from the chamber.

In case of preparing Al-matrix composites, the maximum temperature and pressure needed are separately 720°C and 2,500 psi, respectively - much below the capacity of the HIP equipment. Therefore, the processing can be achieved with a rather simple apparatus.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Different kinds of Al-matrix composites were prepared using the processing method described above. Three commercial aluminum alloys were used as matrix alloys:

- (a) Pure aluminum (170.1)
Chemical composition: Al(99.77%), Fe(0.16%), Si(0.07%).

Fig. 1 Schematic of the apparatus for preparing aluminum-matrix composites.

Fig. 2 Schematic of the temperature and pressure changes during the process used for fabricating aluminum-matrix composites. T_s = solidus temperature; T_l = liquidus temperature.

(b) Al32 aluminum alloy
Chemical composition: Al-1.43Cu-12.13Si-1.3Mg-2.53Ni

(c) 413.1 aluminum alloy (Al-12Si)
Chemical composition: Al(85.98%), Si(11.85%), Fe(0.92%), Cu(0.56%).

Reinforcements were short ceramic fibers, continuous ceramic fibers, SiC whiskers and particulate materials.

SHORT CERAMIC FIBER REINFORCED AL ALLOYS

Fiberfrax HSA Fiber manufactured by Sohio Engineered Materials Company was used as reinforcement. The fiber properties are as follows:

fiber diameter: 1.2 μm (mean),
fiber length: 3 mm,
specific gravity: 2.7 g/cm³,
chemical compositions: Al₂O₃ (43.4%), SiO₂ (53.9%), Fe₂O₃ (2.8%),
TiO₂ (1.6%), K₂O (0.1%), Na₂O (0.1%).

The fibers were suspended in water and separated thoroughly. The preform was made by a combination of suction filtration and pressing. Sometimes a binder was required to improve the stability of the preform. In the present work a silica binder was found to be quite satisfactory. The preform manufacture method was discussed in detail elsewhere by other authors [9,12].

The composite made was sound, with a fiber volume fraction (V_f) of 7.1 vol.%. The binder (silica colloid) content was 5 wt.% of the preform. An Al-12Si commercial ingot was used as the matrix alloy. The melt temperature (T_p , defined in Fig. 2), was 580.0°C as the inert gas pressure began to apply on the surface of the melt. The cooling rate in the A_3 - A_4 period was 3°C/min. It took 35 s for nitrogen gas to increase its pressure in the chamber from 0 to 2,000 psi. The original thickness of the preform along the pressing orientation was 25.5 mm. The final thickness of the fiber reinforced area in the composite decreased to 25.3 mm. The compression deformation due to the pressing operation was less than 0.8%.

Using the squeeze casting method, the corresponding deformation in general is higher than 10%, even as high as 25%. The fiber V_f in the Toyota pistons was 5-7% [8,12,15]. A porous preform with low V_f is weak and can be easily deformed or broken in the pressing operation. The usual way to solve the problem is to increase the amount of the binder in the preform, but excessive binder addition is harmful to the composite, as the remaining binder is mechanically weak and brittle, and it severs the matrix. The method described here offers a way to solve this problem. Even with a small binder content of 5 wt.%, no significant deformation of the preform was observed.

Because of the high hardness of the ceramic fibers, the composites are difficult to machine, even though diamond or nitride edge tools can be used. The problem to produce near-net-shape components has received much attention recently. Due to the small deformation (less than 1%), the method described here can be a new precision technique for eliminating the machining step.

In the squeeze casting method, the ram speed used is about 10 mm/s. At this rate, the infiltration of a 20 mm thick preform takes only 2 s. Because of the unwetting between the preform and the melt, the melt cannot penetrate the preform by its own weight. The infiltration process depends completely upon the huge pressure of 7,000 - 28,000 psi. The pressure which is applied on the melt front of a preform increases so rapidly (within 2 s) that cracks of the preform can be observed in the composite occasionally. The maximum pressure in the new method of this paper was about 2,500 psi., far less compared to that of squeeze casting. It takes more than 30 s to increase the pressure from 0 to 2,500 psi - much longer than the

corresponding time in squeeze casting. We propose that the melt can penetrate a preform completely before the pressure reaches 2,000 psi. We also can take the advantage of a low rate of pressure increase to avoid preform cracks and deformation.

CONTINUOUS FIBER REINFORCED AL ALLOYS

Continuous Nextel 440 ceramic fiber manufactured by 3M Center was used as a reinforcement in the form of a woven fabric. The fiber properties are listed below.

fiber diameter: 10-12 μm ,

density: 3.05 g/cm^3 ,

chemical composition: Al_2O_3 (70%), SiO_2 (28%), B_2O_3 (2%).

The fibers had been coated with an organic polymer, so the fiber cloth was heated to 800°C in an oven in air to remove the polymer finish. The cloth was then cut to the size of the preform and laid up in the chamber. A total of 40 - 60 layers was used to form a preform. The matrices used were Al-12Si alloy and pure aluminum.

A sound composite was prepared with Al-12Si as the matrix at 583.0°C (T_p) and a pressure of 2,500 psi. No evidence of fiber breakage or interfacial reaction in the composite was found by SEM.

In the case of pure aluminum (170.1) used as the matrix, a significant improvement in mechanical strength was noted. The tensile strength of the Nextel fiber cloth reinforced aluminum ($V_f = 0.3$) was 143.5 MPa, as opposed to 60 MPa for pure aluminum.

PARTICULATE COMPOSITES

The particulate materials used as reinforcements were SiC particles (Beuhler) in the 240, 320, 400 and 600 mesh sizes, alumina particles (Beuhler) in the 0.05, 0.3, 1, 5 and 60 μm size, graphite flakes (Asbury #3272) and graphite powder (Fisher Scientific #38). The particles were put into the chamber and then infiltrated. The matrices were pure aluminum and Al-12Si alloy. Examples of such composites are described below.

A sound composite of alumina particle reinforced Al alloy was prepared. The alumina particles, nominally 1 μm in size, were dispersed in the Al-12Si alloy homogeneously. The V_f value was about 0.4. It took 60 s to reach the pressure of 1,230 psi at 578.8°C (T_p).

Alumina particle reinforced Al was also successfully prepared. The particles were about 60 μm in size. The matrix was pure aluminum (170.1). It took 150 s to reach the pressure of 2,508 psi at 660.3°C (T_p).

SiC particles (400 mesh) reinforced pure aluminum (170.1) was also successfully prepared. It took 30 s to reach the pressure of 1,910 psi at 579.2°C (T_p).

The strength and deformability of the particles are also important in processing. The particulate preform made of soft graphite powder (120 mesh or smaller) lacked stiffness, so when the Al melt applied a force on it, the soft particles were squeezed together and all the gaps disappeared and the porous preform could not be infiltrated and became a solid lump. However, if graphite flakes of a size of ~ 500 μm were used to make a preform, the Al melt can infiltrate the preform completely.

SiC WHISKER REINFORCED AL

The whiskers, kindly provided by American Matrix Inc., are β -SiC (cubic) and are stoichiometric, with impurities less than 1000 ppm. The whisker diameter is 1-3 μm , the whisker length is 30-200 μm . The technique to prepare a whisker reinforced metal is almost the same as for a short fiber reinforced metal. The SiC whisker preform had a V_f value of 0.15. SiC whisker reinforced pure aluminum was successfully made under 1,778 psi at 660.9°C (T_p). No change in the preform thickness along the pressing direction was observed.

CONCLUSION

Short fiber, whisker, particle and continuous fiber reinforced aluminum alloy can be produced by the new casting process described in this paper. Sound composite parts were produced under low temperatures (liquidus or near the liquidus) and low pressures (lower than 2,500 psi). Interface reactions between matrices and reinforcements may be alleviated due to the low temperature and low pressure. The process can be used as a near-net-shape method to produce composite parts.

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